

e-ISSN: 3049-0804

Volume 08 Issue 01
Jan-Apr 2026

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Advanced Research Concepts for Video Editing Process of Movies in entire Universe

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ABSTRACT

In the entire universe, so many videos are uploaded and downloaded in different languages; for these, editing, remaking, sound changing, and background changing will be done in all aspects. While these editing processes are happening, one big important observation comes out, which will change the life processes; the creation process also changes, and modification is seen. Here, uploading videos and creating videos through technologies are quite different in all sky levels. Also, the mode of creating videos is different, and the composition of videos is different. Not only single 1D bodies sense level for making videos, but also 2D, 3D, 4D, and ND videos are created in a systematic manner. Also, positive energy species in the Zenith (urdhva sky level) and negative energy species in the Adho Disha (Nadir sky level) are making videos. On the planet Earth, Bhooloka, only physical camera-based instruments are used for creating videos. Some videos using bio-based, which are also called biological, videos from lower sky levels are being created. In 1D, Soul is also making videos, which can be observed from sources. While editing these videos, you can observe very well in a systematic manner. On Earth websites, all kinds of videos are seen; the purpose of making videos is different at different sky levels, which may be from positive or negative energy species.

Keywords:-*Videos, Images, Photos, Editing Process, Prakriti nature videos, soul atma videos*

1. INTRODUCTION

In the science and engineering stream, so many devices are used to capture videos, but it's not quite complete, but also so many videos are made for the attraction of some species. For example, a species that may be a positive or negative type wants to capture some kind of species that they need, such that attraction is made while viewing the planet Earth. Thus, all kinds of species are there in the universe. Suppose Yama has made a video; then an attraction is made on that video, and then Lord Brahma came by the natural process of video. That is, the enemy will be easily attracted. Also, Vishnu made a video, and then, through natural attraction, the rakshasa came into the location. This is the one kind of making videos. Also, Shiva has made a video of the attraction effect, and Asuras came into any location. These are some tricks that gather people to come into personal contact. While editing, so many 1D, 2D, 3D, 4D, and ND species, specifically negative energy species, were observed, which is beyond the concept of nature laws. Once highly negative species easily come into the picture for fear arising, abnormal diseases, and psychic diseases, those who are observing videos suffer. Normally there are 4 kinds of processes made to videos, which are attraction, enchantment, vidveshan, and maran, as death-like kinds of processes are made to videos. In classical videos, films, and movies, which are black and white based, these are the main evidence of the presence of negative energy species as pitrus while in the process of editing one. One has to need image-to-image attraction as an addition process, as well as soul-based single-sense contact sex, which is also a scientific process of video editing. You can't see pitru as a specific negative or positive species; if a person has got this touch of sex, then, that person is able see or else indirect view will be made and gathered from eye as camera.

2. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS:

Negative energy species are present, Positive energy species are present, Soul atma as 1d element present and 2d,3d,4d, and nd species are present.

3. CONCLUSION

- The mode of creating videos is different, and the composition of videos is different. Not only single 1D bodies sense level for making videos, but also 2D, 3D, 4D, and ND videos are created in a systematic manner
- Positive energy species in the Zenith (urdhva sky level) and negative energy species in the Adho Disha (Nadir sky level) are making videos. On the planet Earth, Bhooloka, only physical camera-based instruments are used for creating videos
- While editing, so many 1D, 2D, 3D, 4D, and ND species, specifically negative energy species, were observed, which is beyond the concept of nature laws
- Normally there are 4 kinds of processes made to videos, which are attraction, enchantment, vidveshan, and maran, as death-like kinds of processes are made to videos
- You can't see pitru as a specific negative or positive species; if a person has got this touch of sex, then, that person can able see or else indirect view will be made and gathered from eye as camera
- Negative energy species are present, Positive energy species are present, Soul atma as 1d element present and 2d, 3d, 4d, and and species are present.

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